

**EDUCATION IS THE MAIN DIRECTION OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE
REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract. *This study is based on the modern trends in education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which indicate the great importance of organizing state educational programs and pedagogical methods based on interactive educational strategies. The main goal of modern methods based on interactive educational strategies is to increase the effectiveness of education and increase the student's interest in learning. This study provides information about the advantages of collaborative learning based on educational methods.*

Keywords: *Modern education, educational methods, interactive methods, pedagogical methods, collaborative learning, pedagogical skills.*

TA'LIM O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI RIVOJLANISHINING ASOSIY YO'NALISHI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqot O'zbekiston Respublikasida ta'lim hozirgi kunga kelib zamonaviy yo'nalishlaridan kelib chiqqan holda ta'limga oid davlat dasturlari va ta'limga oid interaktiv strategiyalarga asoslangan holda pedagogik metodlarni tashkil etish muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ta'limning interaktiv strategiyalariga asoslangan holda zamonaviy metodlarni asosiy maqsadi bu ta'lim samaradorligini oshirish va o'quvchining ta'lim olishga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini oshirishdan iborat. Ushbu tadqiqotda ta'lim metodlari asosida kolloborativ ta'lim shaklining afzalliklari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirib o'tilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Zamonaviy ta'lim, ta'lim metodlari, interaktiv metodlar, pedagogik metodlar, kolloborativ ta'lim, pedagogik mahorat.*

Introduction

Today, in modern educational methods based on interactive learning strategies, teaching forms are increasing their adequacy, so the student is not just a recipient of information, but an active participant, a problem solver and a creative thinker. Therefore, the theory and practice of modern pedagogy considers the widespread introduction of interactive strategies and innovative teaching methods into the teaching process to be an urgent issue. Pedagogical methods based on interactive approaches in the education system are a set of strategies that organize the process of acquiring knowledge based on the interaction of students (cooperative learning), active communication with the teacher. According to the analysis of international educational standards, methods based on advanced educational systems of the world serve to develop students'

independent thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills, and interactive teaching methods focused on modern directions of education are identified as the main priority. American educator and scientist John Dewey (1916) in his work "Democracy and Education" emphasized the need to study the educational process in connection with solving real problems in society, and provided information about the advantages of using modern forms of education. Dewey believed that in the learning process, students should learn not only to acquire ready-made knowledge, but also to apply it in practice.

This is based on the concept of "learning through methods" of modern interactive education. An analysis of the results of modern pedagogical research shows that interactive methods based on modern educational programs help to increase students' enthusiasm, independent learning skills, and critical thinking skills. The main goal of the interactive teaching strategy in education is to increase the student's participation in the learning process and ensure his active participation from a passive listener.

The main task is to organize pedagogical methods based on modern educational approaches, which are aimed not only at imparting knowledge, but also at gradually implementing them in areas aimed at the formation of communicative, social, and analytical competencies. The use of such methods in education requires high creativity, pedagogical skills and psychological preparation from the teacher. Based on research conducted by international scientists on interactive methods of modern education, the main analysis of the interactive form of education shows that the level of knowledge acquisition directly depends on the indicators of increasing the student's activity in the educational process.

That is why today, many universities and schools around the world are widely using such educational methods as "Active Learning", "Cooperative Learning". For information, we can say that currently, interactive strategies and pedagogical methods in modern education serve to increase the student's personal interest, broaden his worldview, increase the ability to think independently, acquire new knowledge, learn in a team, develop an educational model based on communication and reflection. The use of methods based on multi-vector pedagogical approaches in education is widely implemented in higher education institutions, increasing the level of student participation in the learning process. Collaborative learning is a proven methodological method that helps students master the content of the curriculum, accelerates the learning process in terms of developing skills in diverse thinking and teamwork.

These pedagogical strategies are widely used in the development of a relatively high level of interaction between students. It is advisable to organize the effectiveness of collaborative learning by ensuring participation in connection with socio-psychological factors (quality of interpersonal relationships, psychological adaptation, positive attitude to learning) and the combination of types of education. The above characteristics of collaborative learning allow us to conclude that it has great educational potential in the areas of collaborative multi-vector education.

This study deeply analyzes the theoretical foundations of pedagogical approaches based on these interactive learning methods, international experience, their application through tools based on modern educational methods, and the possibilities of their implementation in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Analysis of modern education at strategic stages is not only a model of a system that provides knowledge, but also a process that develops a person, prepares

him for social life, teaches him to be active in the environment and the global world. Today, the concept of education is based not on the principle of “knowledge acquisition”, but on the principle of “knowledge creation”, and the use of new methods of education allows us to achieve good results. From a psychological point of view, interactive teaching methods are a tool that ensures the active participation of the individual and helps to consolidate knowledge in long-term memory. According to the theory of social learning of the experienced educator Albert Bandura, a person learns new behavioral patterns by observing, criticizing and analyzing the actions of others.

Therefore, cooperative learning (cooperative learning) and discussion-based methods enhance the interaction of students in the social environment.

Such approaches have formed the concepts of “Differential learning” and “Individual learning paths” in teaching. As a result, the teaching process has become person-centered, flexible and interactive. Thus, the concept and methodology of modern education implies a system built on the basis of person-centered, interactive and collaborative forms of education. The main focus is not on the student's level of mastery, but on the development of his thinking, analysis, creativity and problem-solving skills. Consequently, we believe that the Uzbek education system is also on the path of educating a competitive, knowledgeable, creatively thinking generation in today's global changes by introducing these concepts in harmony with national traditions.

The main model of the interactive education system is a system of analytical methods based on active dialogue, cooperation and exchange of ideas between the teacher and students in the learning process. In this approach, the educational process is divided into two activities: the teacher guides the student, but at the same time learns from the student's thoughts and experience. Interactive strategies radically change the quality of the learning process. International pedagogical research shows that as a result of interactive teaching methods: students' knowledge retention increases by 60-70%, creativity and critical thinking skills develop. Motivation for learning and interest in learning increase. In addition, interactive methods adapt to the student's educational needs. Each student enters the process in a way that suits their abilities, pace and learning style. This approach allows for individualization of education.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that in order to effectively implement interactive teaching methods, the teacher must be highly prepared. Unfortunately, in some cases, the following problems are observed when using interactive teaching methods. Teachers' insufficient knowledge of new pedagogical technologies is a lack of information in applying the methods. To solve these problems, it is necessary to update pedagogical training programs, modernize educational infrastructure, and retrain teachers in digital didactics. Interactive teaching strategies are the basis of modern education. Through them, the student becomes a creator of knowledge, not a recipient of knowledge. These pedagogical methods strengthen the dialogue between the teacher and the student, serve to develop cooperation, creativity, and social responsibility.

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